

RETHINKING THE LAPIS NIGER

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Abstract: At a key location within the Comitium of Rome's *Forum Romanum* lies a collection of stone monuments of significant antiquity. Known as the Lapis Niger, they have become, to use a phrase of recent vogue, a synecdoche. The black stone pavement from which the grouping takes its name has acquired a role as a collective term for the monuments which it covers, just as they, in turn, are often referred to as Lapis Niger. The part standing for the whole. The history of twentieth-century scholarship of these parts has though been characterised, indeed overshadowed, by one aspect of one element of the group – the archaic inscription on one of the stone monuments, the cippus. This paper contends that this monolithic approach has precluded a full appreciation of the significance of both the cippus and the assemblage as a whole, and instead proposes a new approach based on phenomenology, landscape archaeology and the object's own materiality. A decade ago, Andrew Jones called for a new approach to materials-based analysis so as to breach the dichotomy between theoretical archaeologists and science-based archaeologists. He argued for a 'symmetrical form of analysis that focuses not only on the description and characterisation of the material properties of artefacts but also how those material properties intervene in the social lives of people' (Jones, 2004: 335). With this in mind, a more complex, nuanced view is herein advocated; that the entanglement of multiple materials, perspectives, histories, taphonomies and qualities can be explored to arrive at a fuller understanding of the Lapis Niger and its role in shaping and being shaped by early Rome.

The Lapis Niger assemblage was brought to light in a series of excavations by Giacomo Boni in 1899-1900 (Boni, 1899a; Boni, 1900) during which, underneath the fourteen-square-metre black pavement that he discovered (**PLATES 1 & 3**), were found substantial votive deposits (mostly from the sixth/fifth and third/second centuries BC), and a collection of worked-stone objects, which included the following:

- 1) an inscribed cippus (CIL 6.36840), 0.9 metres high, made of Grotta Oscura tufo,¹ dated to the sixth-century BC (Platner, 1929: 483) (**PLATE 2**);

¹ The terminology of archaeologically-relevant lithoid materials has been the source of significant confusion between classical archaeologists, primarily Anglophone, and their counterparts in the earth sciences. The former often use the term tufa as a mistranslation of the Italian *tufo* rather than the scientifically correct tuff (Heiken *et al.*, 2005: 38). This confusion is exacerbated by the existence of an entirely unrelated rock known to geologists as

- 2) a fifth-century BC (Platner, 1929: 483) conical column, 0.48 metres high, of *Monteverde tufo*;
- 3) a discrete structure of the fourth century BC, termed the 'sacellum' or 'Sepulcrum Romuli' (Coarelli, 1999), consisting of a rectangular u-shaped foundation of worked tufo on which were two bases supporting moulded pedestals, which appear to have been the supports for statues of recumbent lions.

Plate 1 - The location of the Lapis Niger showing the black stone pavement, enclosing orthostats, and modern access steps to the monuments beneath. The Column of Phocas (left) and the Decennalia base (right) lie in the mid-ground, with the Basilica Julia beyond.

Plate 3 - Replica of the Lapis Niger Cippus

tufa, resulting in a situation where both disciplines use the same term for completely different materials. In this paper, the word tufo is preferred, though tuff is used synonymously. It is also noted that there is a belief amongst

Plate 2 - The Lapis Niger Pavement in 2004. In November 2008, heavy rain damaged the pavement (Owen, 2008) and to date (2015) the site remains hidden behind a protective awning

It is the first of these objects that concern us here – the stone cippus, whose inscription has been described as Rome’s oldest public document (Palmer, 1969). The ancient boustrophedon text has tantalised and obsessed epigraphists since its discovery. However, here lies our problem. For as a result of this singular scholarship, the cippus has become the text, or rather the apparently legal expression that the text represents. The goal that scholars have addressed themselves towards has been the attempt to decipher and comprehend the text, such that the object itself has become subsumed to the inscription. This lack of a holistic approach has meant that the cippus has been treated as solely a philological challenge, reduced to a squeeze, a record in a corpus, the monument itself having lost its identity as an archaeological object, instead becoming a matrix for a piece of epigraphy. Over the century or so since its discovery, there has been an abstraction of the messages and meanings associated with the cippus, such that its materiality has been overlooked in favour of the law inscribed upon it. The cippus means the law; ‘the materiality of social life has been marginalized ... with the dominant anti-material conception of culture and society’ prevailing (Olsen, 2003: 87). However, the cippus of the Lapis Niger is an object with agency, whose true significance cannot be appreciated by a mono-

disciplinary study of that which is inscribed on it, for this is an object with presence. A presence that, as we shall see, may have carried with it a message even more significant than the inscription.

Before we address this, though, a more thorough understanding of the evidence is needed. And here, we stumble somewhat. The western part of the Forum has a deep and complex stratigraphy, within which little excavation has been conducted, save for the initial clearance of the Campo Vaccino. The first archaeologist of any note on the site was Giacomo Boni, who succeeded Guido Baccelli (the Minister of Public Instruction) as Director of Excavations in the Forum in 1899. His technique seems modern at first, in that he was innovating in the use of draughtsmanship, aerial photography and the combination of multiple disparate disciplines, as well as the use of stratigraphic recording. However, the approach towards stratigraphy was not as we would recognise it today. Boni's method was to excavate fully and then to record the stratigraphy subsequently in section; this he did with particular rigour, recording, for example, 29 strata over six metres in his 1904 excavation of the supposed site of the *Equus Domitiani* (Ammerman, 2015). However, his excavations at the location of the Comitium, though apparently conducted in a similarly rigorous manner, suffered from the same scourge as much of modern archaeology – grey literature. Two reports did appear in *Notizie Degli Scavi di Antichità* (Boni, 1899a; Boni, 1900), but these were more of the form of incomplete field notes relaying first-hand information from the site, without the benefit of careful post-excavation analysis. Boni himself expressed concern that the *Notizie* was not the best place for such a publication and indicated his intention to follow these with a full monograph in *Monumenti Antichi* (Boni, 1899b: 489). This monograph, though, was never completed, as Boni's attention had been diverted elsewhere – the *Equus Domitiani*, Regia and ultimately St Mark's Square in his native Venice.

It was left to others to try to pull together his excavation notes, and perhaps the best synthesis of his work was Gjerstad's attempt to assemble the Comitium excavation's records (1941). This, despite a protracted publication delay of 40 years, rehabilitated some of Boni's fieldwork technique, noting and taking advantage of the way he kept his notes, but still suffered from a lack of some of the most core elements, such as good site plans which to this day compromise successful re-interpretation of the excavations. A second campaign of investigation on the site was conducted by Romanelli in the mid-1950s, but, as Ammerman (1996: 125) has identified, this work was variable in quality and concentrated on the U-shaped altar, and again suffered from protracted publication delays (Romanelli, 1984).

What this picture of excavation history demonstrates is that the record of the investigations conducted during the first half of the twentieth century is weak, and consequently our understanding of evidence presented by those excavations is not as clear as might be hoped. Despite these caveats, it is possible, from the work of Gjerstad and Romanelli, to gain a reasonable understanding of what was revealed in the two campaigns such that we need not summarise it here, save for noting one or two key points. Firstly, the orientation of the Lapis Niger pavement respects the Curia Julia, rather than the monuments beneath, being 36° out of alignment with the sacellum with which it was initially aligned (Gantz, 1974: 354, n. 14). This suggests that its alignment was fixed when the Curia was rebuilt, in more or less its current form, after the fire of 52 BC, and, partly at least, relates to the subsequent rearrangement of the Comitium.

The rearrangement of the underlying monuments onto a single platform, at some more ancient date, is equally interesting (Capodiferro & Taviani, 2003: 154). The platform was that which Gantz believed to be the old Republican Rostra and which Gjerstad identified as being of a yellowish-brown tufo consistent with early works on the Capitoline (*Tufo Lionato*). The careful arrangement and apparent respect for these archaic monuments suggests that their curation and commemoration had in itself significant antiquity. And this veneration of the monuments throughout the history of the site is reflected in Gjerstad's interpretation, in which he has argued for six phases of development (Gjerstad, 1941: 123). In his earliest phase he saw the cippus representing the most ancient, initially standing as an isolated monument but subsequently incorporated into the first phase of the Rostra as an object of respect, to be joined in subsequent phases by the u-shaped altar, which he envisaged as an aedicular shrine. The final phase was the partial demolition of the complex and its sealing off with the Lapis Niger pavement, to which Gjerstad attaches a c. 40 BC date. The commemorative importance of the cippus is, therefore, apparent in the manner in which it, and the other monuments, continued to be respected throughout the development of the surrounding Comitium/Rostra and the relative inconvenience of preserving their location and memorialising their 'power'.

We can therefore begin to get a sense of the objects' materiality and the way in which they manipulated the space around them; a reminder of Rome's history that ought not to be effaced as the city developed. However, as discussed at the beginning of this paper, most scholars have chosen to concentrate on the cippus, seeking to explore and explain the archaic inscription and its meaning (Stroux, 1931; Degrassi, 1957; Gordon, 1983):

QUOI HO [---] / [---] SAKROS ES / ED SOR [---] //
[---] IA [---] IAS / RECEI:IO [---] / [---] EVAM / QUOS:R [---]
[---] M KALATO / REM HA [---] / [---] IOD:IOUXMEN / TA:KAPIA:DOTAV [---]
[---] MI:TE RI [---] / [-----] / [---] M:QUOI HA / VELOD:NEQU [---] / [---] OD IOVESTOD
LOIQUIOD
(CIL 6.36840)

Palmer has provided arguably the most thorough reconstruction of the text, determining it to be a statement of a law concerning a sacred grove that preceded the Comitium – a law against the violation of the place:

Whosoever [will violate] this [grove], let him be cursed. [Let no one dump] refuse [nor throw a body ...]. Let it be lawful for the king [to sacrifice a cow in atonement.] [Let him fine] one [fine] for each [offence]. Whom the king [will fine, let them give cows.] [Let the king have a - - -] herald. [Let him yoke] a team, two heads, sterile ... Along the route ... [Him] who [will] not [sacrifice] with a young animal ... in a ... lawful assembly in a grove ...

(Palmer, 1969: 49)

The king is mentioned in an archaic dative form – *recei* – as is his herald, the *kalator*, and a team of draft animals, which implies a processional route in relation to a sacred grove. The key element here is the mention of the king, though some, including Palmer, have sought to identify this as the Republican *Rex Sacrorum* rather than the monarch himself, leading to his proposition of a post-expulsion date for the cippus. Palmer's dating is based on two aspects of what are essentially the same point, namely that an autocratic king would not need a written inscription outlining his powers nor an inscription providing for his use of a *kalator*, whereas a newly acephalous *Rex Sacrorum* might. This argument though is predicated on reconstructed lacunae in the text rather than clear evidence and, as Holland states, 'the privileges of the Rex Sacrorum and the financing of his ox team hardly concerned anybody except himself, and would be more appropriately inscribed on tablets and stored in the Regia than set to take up room in the place of assembly' (1933: 549). The balance of opinion from Holland and other scholars is that the text should be read at face value in this respect and thus refers to a monarchic king (Frank, 1924: 62; Gantz, 1974: 360; Battaglini, 2009: 39), a position which this paper also adopts. Though the text has been studied in detail by scholars, the impact of the presence of writing at such an early date has not been considered in a purely Roman context (as distinct from Southern Etruria). Literacy

levels at such an early time in Rome's history are likely to have been low, which consequently begs the question – 'what is the function of legal inscriptions, publicly displayed?' (Whitley, 1998: 322). The inscription of the cippus is unlike the large inscriptions of law codes found in public places and which have been traditionally viewed by ancient historians as the harbinger of literacy and, among other things, democracy. This is not a 'Great Code' such as that from Gortyn (c. 450 BC) – a compendium of laws placed in a generalised public space. This is a single specific statement of a single issue, deliberately located at the physical space for which it is relevant. Applied, and in its place. In this sense, it is much closer to the mid-seventh-century Cretan inscriptions from sites such as Dreros, which are short, specific and focus on process and punishment for infringement (Whitley, 1998: 322). Perhaps, therefore, we should be viewing the cippus less as an inscription and more as a monument – it is the stone which lends the inscription its legitimacy, in the sense of being 'written in stone', eternal and permanent. We might even go so far as to consider it as an aniconic image of the law and, through it, the king; an emphasis of the permanence and omnipresence of the monarch and his right to rule. The purpose of short, inscribed law codes such as this is not to encourage debate, but to mystify the laws; 'to ensure that the customs and practices ... appear immutable and unchanging ... the monumentality of such inscriptions appearing all the more imposing.' (Stoddart & Whitley, 1988: 766). So, far from Palmer's argument that such an inscription would not be necessary for a strong monarchy, the Archaic Cretan examples seem to suggest that monumentalising such a statement of law makes it stronger, less open to debate and more fixed, both in time and space – a legitimisation of political authority. The location of these objects, at the heart of Roman political life, continued this authority down the centuries.

The revealing of the black stone pavement in 1900 enabled archaeologists to correlate the remains with several classical texts which describe its agency, most notably that of Verrius Flaccus (late first century BC), whose observation that what had been the tomb of Romulus had now been covered by a black stone *in Comitio* (Festus, *Gloss. Lat.* 177) formed the basis for the identification of Boni's excavated site as the Comitium. Frustratingly, Flaccus does not give a rationale for the burial, but his statement appears to have been connected with a resurgence of the cult of Romulus-Quirinus as a founding deity, and the necessity of neutralising his earthly (though unoccupied) tomb. The context of late Republican politics during which it seems likely that this pavement was installed is of particular relevance, potentially relating to the rise, fall and rise again of the gens *Iulii*. In the aftermath of the Caesarian assassination any reference to Rome's monarchic past must have been highly charged, and the struggle to reconcile their

monarchic origins with the faltering Republic and the potential rebirth of monarchy would have been awkward to navigate. Dionysius of Halicarnassus, writing of his visit to Rome in 36 BC, does not mention the Lapis Niger, which presumably was not yet installed (thereby suggesting a later date than Gjerstad's), instead referring to the two stone lions which he says were the commemoration of the fall of Faustulus:

Some say also that the stone lion which stood in the principal part of the Forum near the rostra was placed over the body of Faustulus, who was buried by those who found him in the place where he fell.

(Dion. Hal. *Ant. Rom.* 1.87.2)

The entirety of Dionysius' comments in the same verse can of course be read as an allegory of contemporary events, reconciling civil strife and looking forward to the city's glorious future: 'gathering together the Latins who had not been slain in the battle ... he built a city on the Palatine hill' (Dion. Hal. *Ant. Rom.* 1.87.3). Varro, however, commenting a few years before Dionysius' visit, returns the complex to Romulus:

Plerique aiunt in Rostris Romulum sepultum esse et in memoriam huius rei leones duo ibi fuisse, sicut hodieque in sepulcris videmus, atque inde esse ut pro rostris mortui laudentur.

(Ps. Acr. on Hor., *Epod.* XVI, 13-14)

Most people say that Romulus was buried in the Rostra and as a memorialization of that, there were two [images of] lions [installed] there, just as we see today on tombs, and also for that reason the dead are eulogized before the Rostra..."

(Woodard, 2013: 56)

What does seem clear, though, is that all three writers are referring to more or less the same place. There is some confusion over who or what is being commemorated, but the repeated references to the stone lions and the connection with the black stone paving suggests that the monuments, the lions and probably the cippus too, were damaged and then collected together during a (Caesarian-Augustan?) rebuilding programme following the Curia fire of 52 BC. The confusion over who was being commemorated with the Lapis Niger group may indeed be explained by the variety of apparently sacred objects enclosed – it is possible that all the traditions are equally valid.

However, the manner in which the monuments were collected, managed and curated by late Republican Rome is also worthy of note. The group, together with the numerous votives and other objects found by Boni, presents us with an insight into how Rome perceived her past. The collection of objects from a range of periods – Monarchy and Republic – and their encapsulation beneath the black stone pavement in what was presumably a single act of conservation, demonstrates a desire to put out of daily sight or use objects which appear to have been exposed for a considerable period of time. Objects which were a reminder of the monarchic past; objects such as the sacellum which as Gantz has suggested may have been embarrassing for the Roman state – ‘Romulus, as a god wasn’t supposed to have any bones’ (Gantz, 1974: 351). These artefacts ceased to be items to be observed and individually venerated. Instead they were put-away with access blocked to them, they were tidied-up, becoming a curated summary of Rome’s histories and creating in turn a unified ‘place of memory’ (Nora, 1992), even if the Romans themselves weren’t entirely clear who or what was being remembered: Faustulus (Dion. Hal. *Ant. Rom.* 1.87.3), Romulus (Festus, *Gloss. Lat.* 177) or even Hostus Hostilius (Dion. Hal. *Ant. Rom.* 3.1.2). These multiple pasts of the Roman people were brought together in a polychronic manner where ‘the character of both human and nonhuman relations with various pasts ... can push back and have an impact within contemporary relations’ (Witmore, 2007: 195). Might we suggest therefore that this new manipulation of Rome’s relationship with her own history is reflective of the changes occurring within the power structure of late-Republican Rome?

This place of memory appears to have acquired a very special status in the late Republic: *niger lapis in Comitio locum funestum significat* (Festus, *Gloss. Lat.* 177). The identification of this spot as a *locus funestus* – a place connected with death, mournful and fatal (Gantz, 1974: 352 n. 8), and its marking with a determinedly black pavement, generated a powerful symbolism – the source of this black stone, this *Marmor Taenarion* (Platner, 1929: 483), is likely Cape Matapan in the Mani peninsula of Greece (Borghini, 1997: 160), where alongside the quarries lies the cave-temple of Poseidon, one of the access points to Hades through which ‘Heracles brought up the hound of Hades’ (Paus. 3.25.4-5). This was the site that Plutarch calls the *Psychopompaeum* – ‘the place where ghosts are conjured up’ (Plut. *De Sera* 17). The very choice of material, the bringing to Rome of the bedrock of Hades’ front-door, echoed, and connected to the spirit of the place as a locus of the dead; a *memento mori* at the heart of the Comitium, that demonstrated a profound sophistication in the use of materials and a skilled manipulation of the messages they conveyed. It was an approach, which as we shall see, had precedents.

Stone choice can then carry a meaning beyond its value as a substrate, or its aesthetic and structural qualities. We should consider this further, and in particular the original use of Grotta Oscura for the cippus. If we accept a sixth-century BC date for the inscription, whether early or late, then the choice of this particular stone must raise questions. This building material does not occur elsewhere in Rome at this time, and does not gain widespread acceptance until after the Gallic Sack (Frank, 1918: 187), so why is it used in this instance? Grotta Oscura is a porous, well-lithified tuff of yellowish-orange colour containing fragments of pumice, and appears to be that which would become known to Vitruvius as *Pallensibus* (Vitr. *De arch.* 2.7.1) and which he describes as *sunt enim aliae molles* (soft and yielding). In the sixth century BC, the source of this material was firmly outside Roman territory, laying on the west bank of the Tiber, five miles north-east of Veii on the east side of the hairpin-shaped valley of the Valle Lunga (Frank, 1924: 61). Consequently, these quarries would have been in the control of Etruscan Veii, and were to remain so until the end of the Third Veientine War. Its use in Rome at such an early date is, therefore, unusual as Rome had ample access to tufo of its own (Heiken et al., 2005). The city was founded on a ready supply of similar material – the Tufo Lionato that we have already encountered and, underlying it, the tufo known as *cappellaccio*, the very first to be exploited by Rome and which found application in the platform of the Temple of Jupiter on the Capitoline and the early phases of the Regia. This Cappellaccio is an olive-grey lithified pyroclastic deposit which outcrops in several places in central Rome, most noticeably on the Capitoline and Palatine and is hence sometimes referred to as *Tufo del Palatino* (Karner et al., 2001: 391). The rock occurs in two deposits, one superimposed on the other with an intervening deposit of Tufo Lionato (Marra et al., 2011: 118) and can be seen today in a massive outcrop on the *Via della Consolazione* (**PLATE 4**), with substantial quarrying activity underlying the Capitoline (**PLATE 5**).

Plate 4 - Outcrop of Cappellacio tuff overlain by Tufo Lionato on the Via della Consolazione.

Plate 5 - Gallery quarries underlying the Capitoline.

With two good quality sources of stone at the heart of the city from earliest times, an explanation must be sought for the importation of Grotta Oscura, as its use is apparently without any obvious justification. Except, that is, for one vital piece of context. This stone, this 'Etruscan Stone', this material foreign and out of place can, if we accept a date for the cippus of somewhere in the sixth century BC, be seen as being in context with another institution, foreign and out of place: the Monarchy itself. It can, therefore, be suggested that the choice of Etruscan Grotta Oscura echoed the Etruscan origins of the traditionally ruling Tarquinii.

Before drawing further towards this conclusion, we should consider the appearance of the cippus, in its original 'Gjerstad 1' phase, within the sixth-century landscape. We have seen how the selection of material for the cippus, and indeed for the pavement five-hundred years later, were both meaningful choices. The question now is how might this choice have impacted upon the surrounding landscape and indeed how might the surrounding landscape have impacted upon it?

The topography of Archaic Rome is extraordinarily difficult to elucidate; there are many metres of made-up ground and clay between what we observe today as the Forum and the underlying natural bedrock, and there have been very few attempts made by archaeologists to push below the level of the site as currently presented to us. Indeed, nobody since Boni's 1904 work on the supposed site of the *Equus Domitiani* has penetrated archaeologically to the natural, six metres below the current forum pavement (Ammerman, 1996: 123). Geological studies can though take us part of the way towards understanding this buried landscape. Marie Jackson's work on the geology of central Rome has brought to light the presence of silted-up channels – the Velabrum Major and Minor – running inland from the Tiber (Jackson et al., 2005; Jackson and Marra, 2006; Jackson et al., 2011). The latter of these crosses the Forum, roughly on the line of the later Cloaca Maxima, and formed a dangerous, marshy area which according to geological coring would have been dry in Summer, but wet in winter, with regular flooding from the Tiber (Ammerman, 1990: 644); it is perhaps this marshiness that is remembered in the myth of Marcus Curtius (Liv. 7.6).

On the ground, the Velabrum Minor cuts through the two tuffaceous hills of the Palatine and Capitoline, forming the high cliffs we have already encountered along the Via della Consolazione, but within the Forum itself the features are more subtle, though nonetheless present, with the valley appearing where the land dips away to the south-east of the Arch of Severus. Albert Ammerman has gone some way to reconstructing the natural topography in this area through a series of augers taken in the 1990s, to reveal the presence of a berm 100 metres

or so wide from the foot of the later Tabularium to the point where the clay of the Velabrum Minor lowers the land (Ammerman, 1990; Ammerman, 1996; Ammerman, 2000). What is of particular note in Ammerman's work is his discovery of several massive outcrops of cappellaccio set into the surrounding Velabrum-deposited clay. These masses are out of place geologically, and would have stood proud in the archaic landscape, some 4 metres higher than the lowest point of the Forum basin. To account for this, Ammerman has proposed a landslip, at some point in geological time, with material from the Capitoline (roughly in the area now occupied by the Temple of Vespasian) having slipped down into the valley to form the three large masses (**PLATE 6**).

Natural ground surface in the north east Forum Romanum

Borehole data from Ammerman 1999

Plate 6 - Digital map of the natural ground surface in the north east *Forum Romanum*. Partial contours show height of natural sixth-century BC ground surface interpolated from borehole data as reported by Ammerman (Ammerman 1996); light green areas show interpolated density of boreholes with Cappellacio mass as buried natural.

Reference Map

It is worth considering how this may have appeared during the sixth-century with the large cliffs that form the religious heart of the city – the Capitoline – seeming to have fallen into the valley. This would have been a striking feature in the landscape, made more so by the marshiness of the lower ground, and the stepping-stone-like connection between the Capitoline and the three masses would have been made even more apparent by their having been of the same material. It might, therefore, have seemed as if the territory of the gods on the Capitoline had slipped down into the territory of man. We should see it therefore as being no coincidence that each of these three masses became locations of significance – the first eventually becoming the Temple of Concord (the Cappellaccio mass is encased within the later *Opus Caementicium* mound), the second (and indeed the only outcrop which is visible today) becoming the Volcanal (**PLATE 7**) and the third becoming the site of the sacred grove, the original location of the cippus, and ultimately the Comitium.

Plate 7 - The Volcanal in the Northern part of the Forum - the only site visible today where the Cappellaccio masses are exposed.

So we have a stone cippus, made of foreign material, sited on a mass of 'special' Roman rock, within a sacred grove, a few metres above a lower-lying marshy area. Both stone types are of markedly different colouration, so one would have stood out when placed upon, or into, another, but not too much – the effect would have been noticeable but not jarring, creamy-yellow on greenish-grey. An Etruscan stone driven into Rome's foundations, but critically lying within the quotidian realm of man – a constructed landscape of meaning through opposition. As Olsen has observed in the case of prehistoric rock art (Olsen, 2003), the rock 'canvas' shapes the art and manipulates the space around it, and here too qualities of the stone mould the meaning of the monument beyond the rather prosaic nature of the inscription. Perhaps this stone was also a reminder of the king's foreign origins and simultaneously an emphatic statement of the king's presence and omnipresence, and the monarchy's role in shaping the fabric of Rome. The cippus both received the king's law and, as we have seen, through its permanence, became a signifier of the law and the king; it was simultaneously product and producer, part of a landscape that 'does not merely reflect reality; it produces reality' (Arrington, 2015: 17). Evidence then of a shaping of the landscape and the beginnings of a cityscape, precisely at the time when scholars consider that Rome first becomes a truly urban city.

Five hundred years later, the actions taken by the late Republic to seal-off these monuments, perhaps as a result of the Curia fire, makes it almost irresistible not to view this as a metaphor for the order-change that was about to take place in Roman politics, a putting away of old politics and histories in an unusually blunt and obvious way, but also a condensing of multiple pasts into a single narrative. The creation of this *lieu de mémoire* forms a symbolic element of the collective and curated cultural memory of the community, the faux-continuity of the Roman state and its ability to retain its Roman-ness despite revolution, civil war and expansion. The creation of the black pavement implies the emergence of a power sufficiently able to create such a construct; the manipulation of cultural memory, and the putting out of site of the monarchic past in the advent of a nascent autocracy: 'in the past, then, there was one national history and there were many particular memories. Today, there is one national memory.' (Nora, 1992: 635-637).

As we approach a conclusion for this paper, the complexity of the interactions, and multiple facets of the assemblage become clearer, as do the inadequacies of archaeology's responses to them. Objects such as the cippus are not isolated; they have multiple agencies. They are not inert; they evolve through different temporalities, during which the original meaning could well have been lost or transmuted and manipulated to suit new agendas.

More than a decade ago, Andrew Jones led the call for a rapprochement between two facets of material culture studies – archaeological science and archaeological theory (Jones, 2004). He sought a symmetrical form of analysis as an approach to these sorts of studies, though as we have seen here, previous scholarship has failed to address itself to this task. The question now is whether the current study has led us further down this path? We have perhaps replaced mono-disciplinarity with an outline of the potentials for multi-disciplinary study but, so far, Jones' symmetrical form of study has not yet been achieved. The immensity of the interactions and dependencies which are needed to develop a full understanding of the objects is beyond what can be attained in this paper, and so the last dependency that the Lapis Niger now demands of modern scholars for its comprehension, is an appreciation of the whole and the myriad dependencies still to be explored: the dependency of the cippus on humans for its maintenance and the knowledge to create it, and on the bedrock for its context, the requirement for other humans to observe the king's law, and the observation of the multiple messages embodied in the stone and the manipulation of space. All are illustrative of the complexity of the entanglements that the Lapis Niger presents and now demand a new interdisciplinarity in its study.

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